

**TABLE TENNIS BENEFITS THE HUMAN BODY, CHILDREN'S
HEALTH AND STRENGTHENING THE IMMUNE SYSTEM.**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648405>

Anatization: One of the main tasks is to select young table tennis players, prepare them in every way, and form their physical qualities, life skills and qualifications.

One of the important means of comprehensive training of young table tennis players is the use of selected types of action games and their application in the training process.

Key words: Young table tennis players, action games, development, physical training, training, physical qualities.

A table tennis tournament is held in our city every year. Fans of this game compete during weekends and after work. In a word, the owners of various professions fight together with healthy competition. It is not surprising: playing table tennis trains not only the body, but also qualities that are very useful at work. After these competitions, new fans will join the ranks of tennis players. It turns out that playing table tennis is not only good for maintaining good physical shape and health. This game helps to develop skills that will help in the professional field and in difficult life situations. The ability to make quick decisions and respond to situations immediately are qualities characteristic of table tennis players. The sport of table tennis was invented by the British. In Uzbekistan, this game was developed at the end of the 19th century. At that time, table tennis was considered only as entertainment. In 1988, table tennis was included in the Olympic Games in Seoul. and confusion by feints is also important. And most importantly, do not lose yourself even for a second, otherwise you will find yourself defeated. Thus, the convenience of the game on the tennis table can be easily adapted to any professional activity.

Table tennis develops attention and resistance to stress. After all, the game is played at an extremely fast speed, hitting up to 180 strokes per minute, this record was set in 2011. The world record is that the ball flies over the net at a speed of more than 160 km per hour!

On average, 200-500 kilocalories are burned per hour of play. Table tennis consumes more energy than basketball. Moving around the table can be compared to running 4-7 kilometers, depending on the intensity of the match. Increase excitement, strengthen the cardiovascular system, perfect form, train

the qualities necessary for a successful career - this is table tennis! And there is no age limit for this game: it is never too late to learn to play table tennis.

Table tennis for children

There is no difference between boys and girls in this sport, it is equally suitable for both. As for age, the department accepts different children, divides them into appropriate groups.

You can play table tennis for children from 6 years old

The ideal age to start training is 6-7 years. It is not recommended to come to the group earlier - this is due to the low ability to concentrate on the subject and in young children associated with a slow reaction. In addition, table tennis tables are standard, there are no special facilities for children. Therefore, the baby cannot learn the technique properly, but only suffers.

If you and your child do not plan to do this sport professionally, he can start at any time later, in any case it will be good for health. But with a few exceptions.

There are a number of contraindications for classes:

- Scoliosis.
- Myopia and retinal diseases.
- Hypertension.

The risk of curvature of the spine is more related to the tension of the muscles of the working arm. If myopia is weak, classes are allowed. But with weak immunity, they are very useful. Consult your pediatrician before introducing your child to sports.

The benefits of table tennis training

In addition to general strengthening of the body, improvement of immunity and physical fitness, the following advantages of "small" tennis can be noted:

- Prevention of visual impairment.
- To teach reaction and good coordination of movements. It can also help in other sports like boxing.
- Development of mental abilities. During the game, the child learns to choose tactics, to use them in practice, to calculate moves.
- Formation of personal qualities such as self-sacrifice, determination to achieve goals, hard work, ability to make quick decisions.
- Development of fine motor skills, strengthening of hand muscles. Improves kidney function and helps to draw.

To relieve tension from the back muscles, you should visit the pool. This prevents curvature of the spine. It is also good to take your child to massage sessions from time to time.

Modern sports today represent many different disciplines and directions, each of which has its own characteristics. One of these sports is table tennis, which has been popular with many people for a long time and has many advantages, the most important of which is the advantages of table tennis, which is played by young and old alike. widely distributed.

An energetic game

Like other sports, table tennis has no age limit and is an energetic game that keeps you fit and healthy, so you can play table tennis at any age. So, anyone can use this game and benefit from it.

Today, this game of table tennis is popular especially among children. The benefits of table tennis for children are many. This is, first of all, the development of gross and fine motor skills in children, improvement of coordination and reaction. In addition, table tennis is always a necessary movement for physical development, table tennis is useful not only for children, but also for adults.

In this case, the pluses of this board game are more numerous and varied. Table tennis requires a lot of energy, so you can easily enjoy this game and stay fit. Table tennis is very beneficial for the player's health. This game allows you to improve breathing and cardiovascular systems, which is important at any age. Due to the mobility of playing table tennis, the respiratory system begins to work more intensively, saturating the whole body with oxygen. This game develops the player's attention, coordination and reaction.

Disease prevention

In addition, table tennis is recommended for people with various vision disorders, including hypermetropia, myopia, etc. In this case, the benefit of table tennis is constant eye training - watching the tennis ball, the player gradually relaxes the eye muscles, which relieves fatigue and improves vision. Table tennis is also useful for hypertensive patients - the gradual improvement of blood circulation helps to stabilize blood pressure. Playing table tennis regularly can improve your overall health, keep you healthy and have a lot of positive emotions during the game. At the same time, regardless of the player's level of preparation, this game will always be useful.

Table tennis is a sport for both professionals and amateurs.

No one doubts the benefits of table tennis. This game is not only useful for the physical development of a person, but also very carefree and exciting. Do not underestimate the powerful psychotherapeutic effect that table tennis brings to

life, and its effect on human systems and organs helps to maintain perfect physical shape until old age.

You don't need many accessories to play table tennis. It is enough to buy a racket, a ball and a comfortable one from the manufacturer in the company

The requirements for tennis tables may vary from player to player.

For example, the better the quality of the tennis table, the easier it is to play table tennis. Tennis tables can be installed indoors and outdoors, tables for adults, tables for children, etc.

The fastest, most agile and most flexible in the world are professional table tennis players. With a ball speed of 120-150 km per hour, opponents have to make a decision and respond with action literally in a few minutes.

To develop and train the vestibular apparatus, doctors recommend playing table tennis, and the training of vision through training is the most perfect of those known. Ophthalmologists advise everyone with various vision problems to play table tennis, including in the postoperative period.

In addition, the intensive form in the complex leads to improved blood circulation in the whole body, normalization of pressure, trains endurance and is considered a type. Due to the large volume of oxygen consumed.

As it turns out, table tennis is developing, artistic ability and calligraphy contribute to the development of handwriting. This sport is shown for children who have poor reading and writing skills.

Everyone knows that table tennis develops muscles, is beautiful and in shape, and also helps to lose weight. A large number of turns and movements, a tense position during the game, its fast pace, small pauses put this type of game in the 5th place in terms of energy consumption.

Therefore, the body consists of the advantages of table tennis, in addition, it is a fun, interesting game, which also contributes to psychological health, helps to cope.

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